

Validation of the TORCH Software Package Based on Measured Data from Pressurized Water Reactor Nuclear Power Plants

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ABSTRACT

The verification and validation (V&V) of core physics design software packages are crucial components in the design and application of pressurized water reactor (PWR) nuclear power plants. V&V represents one of the key research directions in reactor physics. TORCH is a core physics calculation software package independently developed by Nuclear Power Institute of China and has already obtained the safety certification from China Nuclear Safety Administration. The two-step algorithmic workflows and theoretical models of TORCH are presented, including the multi-group library, subgroup resonance treatment, GPU-accelerated MOC transport, predicted-corrected microscopic depletion, Green's function expanded nodal method, and detector reaction rate calculation. The validation was conducted for M310 and Hualong-One nuclear power plant types. Calculation results were compared with measured startup physics experimental and power operation measurement data from Fangjiashan, Fuqing, Zhangzhou and Karachi nuclear power plants. Calculated results include critical boron concentration, isothermal temperature coefficient, control rod worth, and detector reaction rates. The root-mean-square deviation for critical boron concentration is 17 ppm, for control rod worth it is 4.12%, and the maximum deviation for detector reaction rate is 2.10%, all demonstrating that the TORCH software package achieves high computational accuracy compared to measured data.

Keywords: Nuclear power plant, Measured data, V&V, TORCH

1. INTRODUCTION

The core physical design calculation of a pressurized water reactor (PWR) nuclear power plant requires balancing computational accuracy and efficiency. The calculation method needs to satisfy sufficient engineering precision while maintaining good calculation speed to meet various design needs such as fuel loading pattern search and power capability analysis. Given the high demand for computational efficiency in engineering design, the two-step method [1] remains the dominant approach for PWR physical calculations under current computational conditions. The overall strategy involves decomposing the three-dimensional multi-group neutron transport equation into two stages: lattice-level and core-level calculations. At the lattice level, an accurate physical model is used to derive equivalent homogenized cross-sections. At the core level, simplified neutron diffusion equations are solved using few-group homogenized cross-sections. Corrections, such as discontinuity factors, are applied to mitigate the approximations introduced by group and region homogenization in the two-step method.

Software verification and validation are critical components in the software development process, including verification with reference software and validation with experimental data. Among these, validation against measured data more directly reflects the discrepancies between software simulation and real-world measurements, making it particularly important in software development. For pressurized water reactor (PWR) physics design software packages, current validation primarily relies on three types of experimental data: critical test facilities, nuclide measurement experiments, and operational data from PWR nuclear power plants. As for criticality test facilities, early benchmark problems such as Strawbridge-Barry 101 [2] and B&W [3] were established, followed by further enhancement and supplementation based on the International Critical Safety Benchmark Evaluation Project (ICSBEP) [4] and the International Reactor Physics Experiment Evaluation Project (IRPhEP) [5]. As for nuclide measurement experiments, the composition of irradiated fuel nuclides is determined via chemical analysis, leading to the development of the spent fuel nuclide data library

SFCOMPO2 [6]. As for operational data from PWR nuclear power plants, it includes startup physics experiments and power operation measurement data. Besides, the VERA benchmark [7] and BEAVRS benchmark [8] are based on actual modeling parameters from PWR plants with Monte Carlo codes reference solutions.

TORCH is a reactor core physics design software package independently developed by Nuclear Power Institute of China. It includes lattice program KYLIN and core program CORCA-3D. TORCH has been validated using benchmark problems such as VERA, JAEA, and BEAVRS [9] and it has also been verified through criticality experiments (e.g., B&W, Takahama-3, LCT) and burnup tests [10]. This study further conducts verification research on the TORCH software package using PWR nuclear power plants of M310 and Hualong-One types.

2. Theoretical Models Overview of the TORCH Software Package

Figure 1. Calculation framework of TORCH.

The TORCH software package adopts a conventional two-step method. The overall computational framework is illustrated in Figure 1. In lattice calculations, the subgroup method is employed to treat resonance self-shielding effects based on multi-group cross-section libraries. The method of characteristics (MOC) is used to obtain multi-group energy spectrum. A predictor-corrector algorithm is applied for depletion calculations to generate homogenized multi-group cross-sections. The few-group homogenized parameter library is generated through leakage correction calculations, branch calculations, and parameter fitting. In core calculations, few-group parameters are interpolated based on burnup, control rod position, boron concentration, fuel temperature and moderator density. The neutron diffusion equation is solved using the Green's function method. Thermal-hydraulic feedback is incorporated through a single-channel model. Key core physics parameters, such as critical boron concentration and power distribution, are obtained in all burnup steps. Given that TORCH employing conventional theoretical methods, this paper briefly describes only fundamental modules including library, resonance treatment, lattice transport, burnup calculation and three-dimensional diffusion.

1. Multi-group library. The TORCH software package utilizes the HELIOS-format multigroup library [11], which is based on the ENDF/B-VI evaluated nuclear data library and employs a 45-

group energy structure. Considering of the subgroup resonance method, a subgroup parameter library was generated using the Padé approximation fitting method.

2. Subgroup resonance method. The TORCH software package employs the subgroup resonance method to treat resonance self-shielding effects [24]. The subgroup fixed-source equation is solved using the MOC transport method to obtain subgroup fluxes, which are then combined to yield the effective self-shielded resonance cross-section.

3. GPU accelerated MOC transport method. The TORCH software package employs the MOC transport method with Graphics Processing Unit (GPU) acceleration [12]. The MOC method, combined with the aforementioned subgroup resonance approach, theoretically enables the treatment of lattice calculations with various complex geometries. To further improve the computational efficiency of MOC for multiple burnup points and branch calculations, considering of GPU's massive parallel computations ability and limited logic processing capability, a GPU accelerated MOC transport has been built in TORCH. In the GPU accelerated method, the most time-consuming exponential calculations and ray-tracing processes have been transferred to GPU calculation in the MOC workflow.

4. Predictor-corrector micro-depletion method. The TORCH code package employs a micro-depletion method based on the predictor-corrector approach [18]. It solves the burnup equations to calculate nuclide densities in both predictor and corrector steps, while considering nuclide densities from both steps to obtain the nuclide densities for the next burnup step. Three methods were investigated: the traditional predictor-corrector method (PC), the improved predictor-corrector method (PPC), and the log-linear rate method (LLR). The PC method directly uses the nuclide density from the predictor step to solve neutron transport/diffusion equations, obtaining fluxes and reaction rates to calculate nuclide density in the corrector step. This represents the most straightforward predictor-corrector approach. Both PPC and LLR focus on the fluxes and reaction rates obtained in the corrector step, applying linear and log-linear corrections to the reaction rates, respectively.

5. Green's function expansion nodal method. The TORCH code package employs the Green's function expansion nodal method for core diffusion calculations, utilizing source extrapolation and coarse mesh rebalancing techniques to accelerate convergence [14]. Similar to other transverse integration methods, the Green's function expansion method integrates the three-dimensional neutron diffusion equation along two directions. By introducing Green's function expansion and considering discontinuity factors. The nodal flux can then be determined by solving the nodal balance equation.

6. Detector reaction rate calculation method. In detector reaction rate calculation, the detector fission cross-sections are provided by the lattice code and the detector fluxes are from the core code with power reconstruction. The reaction rate is obtained by combination of fluxes and cross-sections.

3. Validation with NPP measured data

The TORCH software package was validated for both M310 (157 fuel assemblies) and Hualong-One (177 fuel assemblies) PWRs using measured data from several nuclear power plants, including Fangjiashan, Fuqing, Zhangzhou NPPs in China and Karachi NPP in Pakistan. The validation covered key physical parameters such as critical boron concentration, isothermal temperature coefficient, and control rod worth in the procedures of startup physics tests and power operation.

3.1. Introduction of validation cases

The validation benchmarks were performed using operational data from pressurized water reactor nuclear power plants, encompassing both the M310 and Hualong-One designs. For M310-type reactors, such as Fangjiashan and Fuqing units 1-4, the core configuration comprises 157 fuel assemblies arranged with an active height of 365.76 cm and equivalent diameter of 304 cm (height-to-diameter ratio 1.20), surrounded by borated water and stainless steel reflectors. These reactors employ three-zone fuel enrichment with initial cycles utilizing borosilicate burnable absorbers, transitioning to gadolinium-based poisons from Cycle 4. The Hualong-One design, implemented at Fuqing Units 5-6, Zhangzhou, and Karachi nuclear power plants, features an enlarged 177-assembly core with 365.76 cm active height and 322.80 cm diameter (aspect ratio 1.13), demonstrating evolutionary fuel management strategies. Fuqing Unit 5, which is the first-of-kind Hualong-One nuclear power plants

Table 1 Detailed results of critical boron concentration in startup physics test.

M310 type reactors			
Fangjiashan U1C1		Fuqing U3C1	
Experiment condition	Deviations/ppm	Experiment condition	Deviations/ppm
ARO	5	ARO	4
Rin	3	Rin	7
RG1in	0	RG1in	7
Hualong-One type reactors			
Fuqing U5C1		Zhangzhou U1C1	
Experiment condition	Deviations/ppm	Experiment condition	Deviations/ppm
ARO	2	ARO	-7
Rin	3	Rin	-5
RG1in	2	RG1in	-5
G1G2N1N2in	-2	G1in	-9
G1in	2	G1G2in	-6
G1G2in	1	G1G2N1in	-11
G1G2N1in	8	G1G2N1N2in	-6

Regarding the isothermal temperature coefficient, validation was conducted with a total of 40 sets of experimental data. Figure 4 presents the calculation results and deviations. The RMS deviation was 0.73% and the maximum deviation of 1.53%. All results were below the engineering design criteria. Specifically, larger deviations primarily occurred in cases where both measured and calculated values were relatively small.

Figure 4 Validation results of isothermal temperature coefficient in startup physics test.

As for the control rod worth, a total of 231 data sets were analyzed and shown in Figure 5. The overall RMS deviation was 4.12%. Seven data points exceeded the 10% engineering criterion, representing 3.03% of total dataset. These exceptions were consistently observed for rods with relatively small worth (SD, N2, N1 positions). Considering unavoidable measurement uncertainties in experimental processes, these calculation deviations are considered reasonable and acceptable.

Figure 5 Validation results of control rod worth in startup physics test.

3.3. Validation with power operation data

The TORCH software package was validated using periodic test data from PWR nuclear power plant power operations, including measurements of core critical boron concentration and detector response current.

With respect to critical boron concentration, analysis of 312 measurements data spanning various units, fuel cycles and burnup levels revealed an RMS deviation of 21 ppm and peak deviation of 62 ppm, as shown in Figure 6. The 50 ppm engineering limit was exceeded in seven cases, representing 2.24% of the dataset. These exceedances occurred exclusively during either the beginning-of-cycle period when xenon equilibrium had not yet been fully established or at end-of-cycle stages where boron burnup effects become more significant.

Figure 6 Validation results of critical boron concentration in power operation.

Figure 7 Validation results of detector reaction rate in power operation.

Regarding detector response current, the validation involved comparing calculated detector reaction rates at corresponding positions with measured current shapes, thereby eliminating potential errors introduced by power reconstruction. A shape normalization procedure was performed by comparing the computational results from the program with the measured current values from the detector, followed by a comparative analysis of the two normalized profiles. In Hualong-One reactor, the detector material is Rhodium. Analysis of the average radial distribution differences in Fuqing nuclear power plant U5C1 power operation showed good overall agreements in Figure 7. The RMS deviation is 1.1% and the maximum deviation is 2.1% occurring in low-power peripheral core regions.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Validation with measured plant data is a critical process in the development and application of PWR core physics design software. TORCH theoretical framework were introduced systematically, including key algorithms such as library, subgroup resonance, GPU-accelerated MOC transport, predictor-corrector micro-depletion, Green's function expansion nodal method and detector reaction rate calculation. The validation utilized startup physics tests and power operation data from multiple nuclear power plants for both M310 and Hualong-One reactor types, covering critical parameters like critical boron concentration, isothermal temperature coefficient, control rod worth, and detector reaction rates.

Startup physics test results demonstrated good agreement with measured data, showing a 17 ppm root mean square deviation and maximum 50 ppm deviation across 61 critical boron concentration measurements, while 40 isothermal temperature coefficient data points exhibited 0.73% RMS and 1.53% maximum deviations. Regarding control rod worth evaluation, analysis of 231 data points yielded 4.12% RMS deviation, with only 7 cases (3.03%) exceeding the 10% acceptance criterion and all occurring in low-worth rod positions where measurement uncertainties are inherently larger. This comprehensive validation confirms the software's accuracy across all key physical parameters.

Power operation validation across 312 burnup points showed a root mean square deviation of 21 ppm and maximum deviation of 62 ppm for critical boron concentration, with seven instances exceeding the 50 ppm engineering criterion. These exceedances were specifically observed either during initial operation prior to xenon equilibrium establishment or near end-of-cycle conditions where boron depletion effects become more pronounced. Additionally, detector reaction rate evaluation indicated all measurements remained within acceptable limits, with the maximum observed deviation of 2.10% occurring in low-power peripheral core regions.

These comprehensive validation results confirm that TORCH achieves good computational accuracy against actual PWR operational data, meeting engineering design requirements for core physics calculations. The software demonstrates robust performance across different reactor types and operational conditions, with observed deviations well within acceptable limits and properly accounted for by known physical phenomena.

In the future, the reflector model will be further optimized by applying different reflector parameters based on their spatial locations, thereby enhancing the prediction accuracy of key parameters such as control rod worth and detector reaction rate distributions.

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